

The Analysis of Association between Anticonvulsants and Bone Mineral Density

Ajay Singh Amera¹, Vijay Singh Amera², Chander Singh Gahlot³

¹ Research Scholar, Department of Pharmacology, BHUPAL NOBLES' University, Udaipur, Rajasthan 313001

² Consultant Anesthetist & Intensivist, Magnus Hospital, Udaipur, Rajasthan.

³ Assistant Professor, Pharmaceutical Science, Bhilwara, Rajasthan, India.

Received: 02-08-2022 / Revised: 29-08-2022 / Accepted: 30-09-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Vijay Singh Amera

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Anti-convulsant drugs are being used increasingly for various conditions including migraine, bipolar disorder, peripheral neuropathy, etc. Along with Conventional anti-convulsants, the newer anti-convulsants are also in use extensively. It is said that the tolerability of newer anticonvulsants is more, but there is rising concern with bone density with the use of anti-convulsants. Many studies have shown that the conventional ones are causing decreased bone mass density leading to fractures.

Aims and Objectives: To evaluate the significant effect on bone mass density due to usage of different anti-convulsants.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective study assessed the patients for Bone Mineral Density, who were on anti-convulsants for various conditions. According to the patients' exposure to anticonvulsants, they were classified into five groups. Among them, one of the groups (group 5) was not exposed to anti-convulsant and were considered as the reference group for comparing T-scores with the other groups.

Results: It has been observed that T-score is lower with conventional anticonvulsants while newer anticonvulsants (both group 1 and group 2) caused significant ($P < 0.01$) T-score compared to the unexposed or reference group, when femoral neck is considered. In all the anatomical sites including femoral neck, lumbar spine and hip, T-score in group 2 came to be significantly higher ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The study has concluded that newer anti-convulsants does not cause decrease of bone mass density and therefore, there is no risk of causing fractures with the usage of newer anti-convulsants.

Keywords: Anticonvulsants, Bone Mineral Density, Migraine, Gabapentine

This is an Open Access article that uses a fund-ing model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

It has been long known that drugs used in treatment of epilepsy have been long associated with bone disease [1]. Studies that were initially done in this field exhibited florid bone [2] disease which was confirmed after pathological biopsies [3]. But the limiting factor here was that these were performed on mainly on

institutionalized patients that had many otherwise common factors like improper diet, restricted outdoor activity in sunlight, no/ limited exercise that would have likely influenced the results thus obtained [4]. Since then, many advances have occurred and revelations from studies done on ambulatory people state that they suffer

from radiographic [5,6] and biochemical abnormalities [7,8,9] along with reduced bone mineral density (BMD) [10, 11]. Much frequent bone mineral metabolism anomalies have also been reported from them [12,13]. The most common occurring feature of experiencing frequent fractures [14, 15] is a vital characteristic found in epileptic patients on AEDs [16, 17]. A latest and very sensitive DXA technique is now operating that can detect 5% (and even lesser) bone mass decrement [18]. Children suffering from this disease exhibit diminished whole-body bone mass (19) along with other specific losses like axial & appendicular bone loss. The most frequent types of anomalies that characterize this particular situation are “hypocalcemia, hypophosphatemia, reduced serum levels of biologically active vitamin D metabolites, and hyperparathyroidism”. Amount of bone turnover markers found, related of bone formation and bone resorption also can be detected beyond acceptable norms. Calcium is an important element related to bones whose homeostasis gets hampered AEDs [20]. The chances where hypocalcemia can deteriorate bone health vary from 3% - 30% [21,22, 23]. In these kinds of patients serum phosphate also declines [24, 25]. The important vitamin for bone health the vitamin D [26] which is expressed in terms of serum 25(OH)D concentration [27] that expresses the vitamin D status [28,29] of any being, is found to be reduced in adult patients as well on AEDs drugs [30, 31]. The parathyroid gland present in human body is secretes that holds high importance in calcium level monitoring a hormone that (PTH) is secreted by the parathyroid gland and is directly involved in calcium regulation; as serum calcium gets diminished secretion of parathyroid hormone gets triggered leading to bone breakdown/resorption & AED therapy is known to enhance the release of this hormone in the body [32]. There are certain kind of markers that indicate formation of bone in the body like

osteocalcin; one among them is Alkaline phosphatase whose secretion is enhanced in patients of all ages [24,25], this substance despite of being a vital component lacks sensitivity and specificity (as it has many sources of origin). Osteocalcin, an indicator of declining bone health is known to elevate in patients on AED therapy [33]. There are certain medicines generally used in epilepsy that are also known for their impairment of bone metabolism and are also responsible for wearing bone density; they include phenytoin, Phenobarbital, carbamazepine etc. [34]. Earlier almost no deleterious effects of valproate (VPA) on bones [29] were recognized. But now a study on 40 patients [10] under long-term valproate reported enhanced bone resorption and formation markers and serum calcium and reduced serum 1,25[OH]₂D concentration. DXA results from the same study [10] reported about 14% BMD reduction in group consuming VPA monotherapy (adult patients) when seen parallel to group comprising healthy controls. Experimental works on children with epilepsy exhibit that those on VPA therapy had lesser BMD [35,36]. A study on kids about impact of VPA (alone) or on combo of lamotrigine and VPA concluded on the patients suffering from low bone mass, and reduced bone formation & short stature were commonly caused [19]. Bones were at higher risk in cases of Polytherapy [37].

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This cohort study is of retrospective design which derived its data from ABC Hospital. The patients were assessed for Bone Mineral Density by employing Dual Energy X-Ray (DXA) between December, 2021 and May, 2022. It is a standard clinical practice that patients who are on anticonvulsants should be screened with DXA. The patients are grouped according to their exposure to number and types of groups

anticonvulsants. T-scores of BMD were assessed for determining the outcome of the BMD status of the patient. Applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, the study considered 125 patients in total.

According to the patients' exposure to anticonvulsants, they were classified into five groups. Group 1 patients are those who were on newer enzyme-inducing anticonvulsants (like topiramate), group 2 patients are those who took newer nonenzyme-inducing anticonvulsants like levetiracetam or gabapentin, group 3 patients are those who took conventional enzyme-inducing anticonvulsants like phenytoin, group 4 patients are those who were on conventional nonenzyme-inducing anticonvulsants like valproic acid and group 5 patients who did not take any anticonvulsants. Group 5 patients were considered as the reference group with whom, T - score of all other groups were compared.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

The patients who were included in this study are those who received treatment from our hospital, tested for BMD assessment and cooperated with our hospital protocol. The patients who were excluded from the study are those who did not complete the whole study protocol and patients with other chronic conditions.

Data Assessment and Management

The data regarding Bone Mineral Density reports were considered from the patients' records and T-scores of BMD were determined and recorded for femoral neck, total hip, lumbar spine, osteopenia or

osteoporosis. The measurement of BMD was done by densitometer. DXA was performed by experienced radiologist. If the radiologist has taken more than one result of DXA, then, the most recent one was considered.

The study also considered determination of Body Mass Index (BMI) from patient's height and weight, history of drugs, its dosage and duration of the drug treatment. The baseline characteristics of the patients considered for this study were recorded including their prescribed anticonvulsant class. The patients were grouped according to their exposure to anticonvulsants. Even they were classified according to the number of classes of anticonvulsants prescribed. The outcome on the study population was determined by T-score.

Statistical Analysis

The study used SPSS 25 and excel software for statistical analysis and other analyses. The descriptive data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The study has employed χ^2 test for analyzing categorical variables while student *t*-test has been used for continuous variable. The level of significance was considered to be $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results

The study has recorded baseline characteristics of the whole study population. The study has classified them in each group and equal number of patients have been assigned to each group. The

Table 1: Basic characteristics of the study population in each group

Characteristic	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5
Number of patients (N)	25	25	25	25	25
Age ^a	55.25 \pm 12.22	54.15 \pm 11.89	51.25 \pm 11.56	53.25 \pm 11.52	54.12 \pm 10.36
Male	15	16	18	13	15
Female	10	09	07	12	10
Body Mass	25.6 \pm 3.2	24.9 \pm 3.8	26.1 \pm 2.9	26.5 \pm 2.8	25.2 \pm 3.3

Index (BMI) ^a					
Alcohol users ^b	15, 60%	16, 64%	13, 52%	14, 56%	15, 60%
Previous history of fracture ^b	3, 12%	2, 8%	2, 8%	3, 12%	2, 8%
Corticosteroidusers ^b	4, 16%	3, 12%	1, 4%	3, 12%	2, 8%
Vitamin D users ^b	3, 12%	2, 8%	2, 8%	1, 4%	2, 8%

^aExpressed as mean value \pm standard deviation

^bExpressed as number of patients followed by the percentage of patients in that group

The study has found that the use or exposure to anticonvulsant agents to the patients, does not necessarily lower Bone Mass Density. It has been observed that T-score is lower with conventional anticonvulsants while newer anticonvulsants (both group 1 and group 2) caused significant ($P < 0.01$) T-score compared to the unexposed or reference group, when femoral neck is considered. Therefore, the bone density increased with newer anticonvulsant as compared to the conventional ones. But in case of lumbar spine or total hip bone, there is hardly any significant changes in T-scores with respect to the reference group. Again, group 2 patients who were given newer non-enzyme anticonvulsant agents showed significantly higher T-score with respect to the patients of reference group. In all the anatomical sites including femoral neck, lumbar spine and hip, T-score in group 2 came to be significantly higher ($P < 0.05$).

Table 2: The mean difference in T - scores between each group and group 5 (reference group)

		Femoral Neck	Lumbar spine	Total Hip
Group 1	Mean T-score	0.13	0.11	0.07
	P-value ^a	< 0.01	0.08	0.06
Group 2	Mean T-score	0.07	0.09	0.05
	P-value ^a	< 0.01	<0.01	0.04
Group 3	Mean T-score	- 0.03	0.05	- 0.03
	P-value ^a	0.48	0.268	0.025
Group 4	Mean T-score	0.06	-0.06	0.02
	P-value ^a	0.059	0.395	0.041

^aP-value is computed between respective group with that of group 5 (reference group)

Discussion

There exist many possible theories that establish a relation between AEDs and bone disease. We shall be discussing over here a few of the possible ones of them. There is hepatic induction of the cytochrome P450 enzyme system that aggravates catabolism of vitamin D which is one of the dominant reasons reported [38]. But it was a contradiction to other similar studies that were based those medicines (viz. VPA) that hamper functioning of cytochrome P450 enzyme

system. All studies are not unanimous on the concept of insufficiency of vitamin D also as there are studies that exhibit bone turnover which is not dependent on vit. D [32,34]. Few more to list possibilities comprise of- improper parathyroidism functioning, decreased concentration of calcitonin [38] etc. Those drugs that cause secretion of hepatic cytochrome P450 enzymes might unnecessarily change useable form of vit. D to inactive metabolites (liver microsomes are

responsible for this action); this process is known to limit availability of vitamin D [39]. This triggers the intestinal mucosa to reduce calcium absorption that results into hypocalcemia which stimulates the parathyroid to release more parathyroid hormone, which in turn aggravates bone turnover by mobilizing bone calcium stores [40, 41].

Bone loss management in women-

Women of elderly age group not on antiepileptic drugs (but irregular calcium intake) can improve bone health by increasing calcium uptake (supplements, sunlight and otherwise) [42]. In postmenopausal women hormone replacement is capable of reducing bone loss [42]. But its side effects are much more damaging and include mainly –malignancy of breast region, cardiac ailments etc. [43]. Also, in epileptic females this therapy accelerates seizure activity [44].

Hip joint and epilepsy drugs- When two different groups of patients receiving EIAED & non-EIAED were compared no significant findings were obtained in values of bone mineral density in ‘the Ward triangle, trochanter, or total hip’. It was thus concluded that one ROI might report bone resorption and other might exhibit normal bone mineral density. It was also suggested that accumulation and discussion of vast data available ‘on the femoral neck, greater trochanter, and Ward triangle into total-hip BMD’ could result into misinterpretation of results concerning changes in BMD in these regions. An agreement on this was gained out of study by Selby *et al.* who declared there might be errors while resolving information derived from the hip subregions (59%) while deciding bone mineral density hence it cannot be implied to extract any clinically meaningful outcome [45]. Also, as various type of scanners are utilized in hip subregion significant difference might happen while working on total-hip calibration formulas; hence application of subregion calibration

formulas is suggested only while calibrating absolute changes [46].

Although well accepted and established that treating the disease with more than one type of drug enhances chances of fracture in post-reproductive females [51] but study by [49] found contradicting results and did not notice any such finding in their study. The probable reason might be either the type of population chosen for the study, or the choice of drugs taken into consideration. Moving forward with gender specific studies we wish to state here the study by

Andress *et al.*, who reported age and duration of treatment as critical risk factors for low BMD in men receiving AEDs [47], but this was refuted by the study by [49] which concluded that both these factors are not responsible for laying any influence on bone health of males. This discrepancy could be because the study [49] comprised of patients of both genders and most of them were on combination therapy. A study comprised on usage of latest drugs like gabapentin, lamotrigine, and topiramate reported that in patients receiving these drugs incidences of osteoporosis are much lesser ‘at the lumbar spine, femoral neck, and total hip’ [48]. It has been observed that patients receiving carbamazepine monotherapy (33 patients) suffered bone loss at lumbar and femoral neck, on the contrary another group that was provided with valproate (22 patients) or some kind of polytherapy exhibited bone mineral density that matched very near to that of the control group [49].

Chou *et al.* in their pediatric study revealed that those children that were getting carbamazepine monotherapy reported lesser bone density, than those on having valproate monotherapy [50]. Smoking might be or might not be related with bone loss [52].

Conclusion

The study has concluded that the usage of newer anticonvulsant agents for longer

time is associated with lower BMD. The study has inferred that the T-score of newer nonenzyme - inducing anticonvulsants like levetiracetam or gabapentin, are significantly higher than individuals who have no exposure to anticonvulsants. Thus, newer nonenzyme - inducing anticonvulsants should be prescribed for shorter duration for avoiding increase of T-score. The author also suggests conducting more studies evaluating relationship between anticonvulsants and T-score, on larger and more varied population. However, this current study has efficiently brought forward the significant relationship between anti-convulsant exposure and BMD, which can further add to the clinical guidance regarding the treatment involving anti-convulsants to the individuals with abnormalities in bone mass density. However, the study has concluded that newer anti-convulsants does not cause decrease of bone mass density.

References

- Dent CE, Richens A, Rowe DFJ, Stamp TC. Osteomalacia with long-term anticonvulsant therapy in epilepsy. *Br Med J* 1970;4: 69–72.
- Richens A, Rowe DFJ. Disturbance of calcium metabolism by anticonvulsant drugs. *Br Med J* 1970;4: 73–76.
- Hunter J, Maxwell JD, Stewart DA, Parsons V, Williams R. Altered calcium metabolism in epileptic children on anticonvulsants. *Br Med J* 1971;4:202–204.
- Hoikka V, Savolainen K, Alhava EM, Sivenius J, Karjalainen P, Repo. Osteomalacia in institutionalized epileptic patients on long-term anticonvulsant therapy. *Acta Neurol Scand* 1981;64: 122–131.
- Stephen LJ, McLellan AR, Harrison JH, Shapiro D, Dominiczak MH, Sills GJ, Brodie MJ. Bone density and antiepileptic drugs: a case-controlled study. *Seizure* 1999;8: 339–342.
- Sheth RD, Wesolowski CA, Jacob JC, Penney S, Hobbs GR, Riggs JE, Bodensteiner JB. Effect of carbamazepine and valproate on bone mineral density. *J Pediatr* 1995;127: 256–262.
- Chung S, Ahn C. Effects of anti-epileptic drug therapy on bone mineral density in ambulatory epileptic children. *Brain Dev* 1994;16: 382–385.
- Timperlake RW, Cook SD, Thomas KA, Harding AF, Bennett JT, Haller JS, Anderson RM. Effects of anticonvulsant drug therapy on bone mineral density in a pediatric population. *J Pediatr Orthop* 1988;8: 467–470.
- Valimaki MJ, Tiihonen M, Laitinen K, Tahtela R, Karkkainen M, Lamberg-Allardt C, Makela P, Tunninen R. Bone mineral density measured by dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry and novel markers of bone formation and resorption in patients on anti-epileptic drugs. *J Bone Miner Res* 1994;9: 631–637.
- Sato Y, Kondo I, Ishida S, Motooka H, Takayama K, Tomita Y, Maeda H, Satoh K. Decreased bone mass and increased bone turnover with valproate therapy in adults with epilepsy. *Neurology* 2001;57: 445–449.
- Farhat G, Yamout B, Mikati MA, Demirjian S, Samaya R, El-Hajj Fuleihan G. Effect of antiepileptic drugs on bone density in ambulatory patients. *Neurology* 2002;58: 1348–1353.
- Andress DL, Ozuna J, Tirschwell D, Grande L, Johnson M, Jacobson AF, Spain W. Antiepileptic drug-induced bone loss in young male patients who have seizures. *Arch Neurol* 2002;59: 781–786.
- Tsukahara H, Kimura K, Todoroki Y, Ohshima Y, Hiraoka M, Shigematsu Y, Tsukahara Y, Miura M, Mayumi M. Bone mineral status in ambulatory

- pediatric patients on long-term anti-epileptic drug therapy. *Pediatr Int* 2002;44: 247–253.
14. Jaglal SB, Kreiger N, Darlington GA. Lifetime occupational physical activity and risk of hip fracture in women. *Ann Epidemiol* 1995;5: 321–324.
 15. Cummings SR, Nevitt MC, Browner WS, Stone K, Fox KM, Ensrud KE, Cauley J, Black D, Vogt TM. Risk factors for hip fracture in white women: Study of Osteoporotic Fractures Research Group. *N Engl J Med* 1995;332: 767–773.
 16. Desai KB, Ribbans WJ, Taylor GJ. Incidence of five common fractures in an institutionalized epileptic population. *Injury* 1996;27: 97–100.
 17. Vestergaard P, Tigarán S, Rejnmark L, Tigarán C, Dam M, Mosekilde L. Fracture risk is increased in epilepsy. *Acta Neurol Scand* 1999;99: 269–275.
 18. LeBlanc AD, Schneider VS, Engelbretson DA, Evans HJ. Precision of dual photon absorptiometry measurements. *J Nucl Med* 1986;27: 1362–1365.
 19. Guo C, Ronen GM, Atkinson SA. Long-term valproate and lamotrigine treatment may be a marker for reduced growth and bone mass in children with epilepsy. *Epilepsia* 2001;42: 1141–1147.
 20. Hahn TJ, Hendin BA, Scharp CR. Effect of chronic anticonvulsant therapy on serum 25-hydroxycalciferol levels in adults. *N Engl J Med* 1972;287: 900–904.
 21. Bouillon R, Reynaert J, Claes JH, Lissens W, De Moor P. The effect of anticonvulsant therapy on serum levels of 25-hydroxyvitamin D, calcium, and parathyroid hormone. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 1975;41: 1130–1135.
 22. Berry JL, Mawer EB, Walker DA, Carr P, Adams PH. Effect of antiepileptic drug therapy and exposure to sunlight on vitamin D status in institutionalized patients. In: Oxley J, Janz J, Meinardi H, eds. *Antiepileptic therapy: chronic toxicity of antiepileptic drugs.*: Raven Press, 1983: 185–192.
 23. Gough H, Goggin T, Bissessar A, Baker M, Crowley M, Callaghan N. A comparative study of the relative influence of different anticonvulsant drugs, UV exposure and diet on vitamin D and calcium metabolism in outpatients with epilepsy. *Q J Med* 1986;230: 569–577.
 24. O'Hare JA, Duggan B, O'Driscoll D, Callaghan N. Biochemical evidence for osteomalacia with carbamazepine therapy. *Acta Neurol Scand* 1980;62: 282–286.
 25. Bogliun G, Beghi E, Crespi V, Delodovici L, d'Amico P. Anticonvulsant drugs and bone metabolism. *Acta Neurol Scand* 1986;74: 284–288.
 26. Skillen AW, Peirides AM. Serum gamma glutamyl transferase and alkaline phosphatase activities in epileptics receiving anticonvulsant therapy. *Clin Chim Acta* 1976;72: 245–251.
 27. Okesina AB, Donaldson D, Lascelles PT. Isoenzymes of alkaline phosphatase in epileptic patients receiving carbamazepine monotherapy. *J Clin Pathol* 1991;44: 480–482.
 28. Brown AJ, Dusso A, Slatopolsky E. Vitamin D. *Am J Pediatr Renal Physiol* 1999;277: F157–F175.
 29. Davie MW, Emberson CE, Lawson DE, Roberts GE, Barnes JL, Barnes ND, Heeley AF. Low plasma 25-hydroxyvitamin D and serum calcium in institutionalized epileptic subjects: associated risk factors, consequences and response to treatment with vitamin D. *Q J Med* 1983;205: 79–91.
 30. Stamp TCB, Round JM, Haddad JG. Plasma levels and therapeutic effect of 25-hydroxycholecalciferol in epileptic patients taking anticonvulsant drugs. *Br Med J* 1972;4: 9–12.
 31. Tjellesen L, Christiansen C. Serum

- vitamin D metabolites in epileptic patients treated with 2 different anticonvulsants. *Acta Neurol Scand* 1982;66: 335–341.
32. Weinstein RS, Bryce GF, Sappington LJ, King DW, Gallagher BB. Decreased serum ionized calcium and normal vitamin D metabolite levels with anticonvulsant drug treatment. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 1984;58: 1003–1009.
 33. Takeshita N, Seino Y, Ishida H, Seino Y, Tanaka H, Tsutsumi C, Ogata K, Kiyohara K, Kato H, Nozawa M, Akiyama Y, Hara K, Imura H. Increased circulating levels of gamma-carboxyglutamic acid-containing protein and decreased bone mass in children on anticonvulsant therapy. *Calcif Tissue Int* 1989;44: 80–85.
 34. Verrotti A, Greco R, Latini G, Morgese G, Chiarelli F. Increased bone turnover in epileptic patients treated with carbamazepine. *Ann Neurol* 2000;47: 385–388.
 35. Kafali G, Erscelan T, Tanzer F. Effect of antiepileptic drugs on bone mineral density in children between ages 6 and 12 years. *Clin Pediatr* 1999;38: 93–98.
 36. Akin R, Okutan V, Sarici I, Altunbas A, Gokcay E. Evaluation of bone mineral density in children receiving antiepileptic drugs. *Pediatr Neurol* 1998;19: 129–131.
 37. Gough H, Bissesar A, Goggin T, Higgins D, Baker M, Crowley M, Callaghan N. Factors associated with the biochemical changes in vitamin D and calcium metabolism in institutionalized patients with epilepsy. *Ir J Med Sci* 1986;155: 181–9.
 38. Pack AM, Morrell MJ. Adverse effects of antiepileptic drugs on bone structure: epidemiology, mechanisms, and therapeutic implications. *CNS Drugs* 2001;15: 633–642.
 39. Perucca E. Clinical implications of hepatic microsomal enzyme induction by anti-epileptic drugs. *Pharmacol Ther* 1987;33: 130–144.
 40. Koch HV, Kratf D, von Herrath D. Influence of diphenylhydantoin and phenobarbital on intestinal calcium transport in the rat. *Epilepsia* 1972;13: 829–841.
 41. Pack, A. M. (2003). The association between antiepileptic drugs and bone disease. *Epilepsy currents*, 3(3), 91-95.
 42. Delmas PD. Treatment of postmenopausal osteoporosis. *Lancet* 2002;359: 2018–2026.
 43. Writing Group for the Women's Health Initiative investigators. Risks and benefits of estrogen plus progesterone in healthy postmenopausal women: principal results from the Women's Health Initiative randomized controlled trial. *JAMA* 2002;288: 366–368.
 44. Harden CL, Pulver MC, Ravdin L, Javobs AR. The effect of menopause and perimenopause on the course of epilepsy. *Epilepsia* 1999;40: 1402–1407.
 45. Selby P. L., McCloskey E. V., Robinson J., Smith I. G., Potts B., Beneton M. N. C., & Kanis J. A. Is a calculated total hip BMD of clinical use? *Osteoporosis international*, 2000;11(4): 368-371.
 46. Lu, Y., Fuerst, T., Hui, S., & Genant, H. K. (2001). Standardization of bone mineral density at femoral neck, trochanter and Ward's triangle. *Osteoporosis international*, 2001; 12(6): 438-444.
 47. Andress D. L., Ozuna J., Tirschwell D., Grande L., Johnson M., Jacobson A. F., & Spain W. Antiepileptic drug-induced bone loss in young male patients who have seizures. *Archives of neurology*, 2002;59(5): 781-786.
 48. Lee, R. H., Lyles, K. W., Sloane, R., & Colón-Emeric, C. The association of newer anticonvulsant medications and bone mineral density. *Endocrine practice: official journal of the American College of Endocrinology and the American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists*. 2012.
 49. Salimpour H., Kazerooni S.,

- Seyedabadi M., Nabipour I., Nemati R., Iranpour D., & Assadi M. Antiepileptic treatment is associated with bone loss: difference in drug type and region of interest. *Journal of nuclear medicine technology*, 2013; 41(3): 208-211.
50. Chou I. J., Lin K. L., Wang H. S., & Wang C. J. Evaluation of bone mineral density in children receiving carbamazepine or valproate monotherapy. *Acta paediatrica Taiwanica. Taiwan er ke yi xue hui za zhi*, 2007;48(6): 317-322.
51. Carbone L. D., Johnson K. C., Robbins J., Larson J. C., Curb, J. D., Watson K. & LaCroix A. Z. Antiepileptic drug use, falls, fractures, and BMD in postmenopausal women: findings from the women's health initiative (WHI). *Journal of bone and mineral research*, 2010;25(4): 873-881.
52. Lyngstad-Brechan M. A., Taubøll E., Nakken K. O., Gjerstad L., Godang K., Jemtland R., & Bollerslev J. Reduced bone mass and increased bone turnover in postmenopausal women with epilepsy using antiepileptic drug monotherapy. *Scandinavian journal of clinical and laboratory investigation*, 2008;68(8):759-766.